
116. The Arcturus and HR 1614 streams

IN ESSAY #115, I summarised what was known, pre-Gaia, about the dozen or so ‘moving groups’ in the solar neighbourhood; these are stars with coherent kinematics, non-circular Galactic bulk motions, and peculiar velocities well above the velocity dispersion of field stars of comparable age. Olin Eggen, who had pioneered the study of these groups or streams, considered that they were the ‘evaporating’ remnants of open clusters.

Today, we know that some of these groups indeed have such an origin, with tidal tails stretching out along their parent cluster’s orbit through the Galaxy. Most clearly seen in the Gaia data are coherent groups in the solar neighbourhood associated with the Hyades cluster (essay #20), the Pleiades cluster (#13), and with other more distant open clusters such as Palomar 5 (#109).

BUT WE NOW KNOW that the kinematic groups of older stars fall into (at least) three other categories. The first are coherent streams of halo stars, interpreted as the tidal debris of satellite galaxies long ago accreted by the Milky Way, first identified from the Hipparcos space velocities by Helmi et al. (1999), and with Enceladus and several others recently discovered in the Gaia data (#59).

The second category of local kinematic groupings are those attributed to resonant trapping by the gravitational potential of our Galaxy’s rotating bar and/or spiral arms. The archetype is the Hercules stream, which I looked at in my previous essay. Another possibility is that they arise from processes such as phase mixing (in position and velocity) of dissolving spiral structure, or phase mixing due to external perturbations.

TODAY, WITH THE data from Gaia, we can study the kinematic groups in our solar neighbourhood hypothesised by Eggen (and others), and examine whether they have originated through cluster evaporation, tidal capture, resonant trapping, or external perturbations. And whether there is evidence for previously unknown kinematic groupings in the solar neighbourhood.

The overall goals are, of course, to gain further insight into the formation history of the Milky Way and its stellar populations.

HERE I WILL look at just two of the other known kinematic groups in the solar neighbourhood: the Arcturus stream, and the HR 1614 kinematic group. Both have been subject to debate as to their nature, and in both cases, Gaia has thrown new light on their origins.

FIRST, ARCTURUS. Eggen (1971) discovered an overdensity of some 50 stars, including Arcturus, with similar space velocity components, $V \approx -100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (In Galactic UVW coordinates, U is in the direction of the Galactic centre, V in the direction of Galactic rotation, and W is towards the north Galactic pole).

Today, Eggen’s idea that the stars had escaped from an open cluster is disfavoured, especially given the spread of chemical abundances. Rather, three other origins of the Arcturus stream have been proposed.

Navarro et al. (2004) and Helmi et al. (2006) concluded that their angular momentum is too low to arise from dynamic perturbations induced by the bar, while their low metallicity and similar apocentres are consistent with them originating from an accreted satellite.

But Antoja et al. (2009) and Gardner & Flynn (2010) could not rule out that it might be a resonance feature associated with the Galaxy’s bar. Meanwhile, Minchev et al. (2009) suggested that it represents an unrelaxed disk population which might have been left following a perturbing event some 1.9 Gyr ago.

A MAJOR STUDY using the Gaia DR2 data has been made by Kushniruk & Bensby (2019). They constructed space velocities, angular momenta, and actions (conserved quantities that characterise stellar orbits) for more than 5.8 million stars within 5 kpc. They used a wavelet transform to characterise kinematic overdensities in the disk, and used these to select possible group members from spectroscopic surveys (GALAH and APOGEE) to study their chemical properties.

They actually searched for streams in four different planes defined by combinations of velocity (UVW), angular momentum (L), and action components (J); specifically in the $U-V$ plane, the $V - \sqrt{U^2 + 2V^2}$ plane, the $L_z - \sqrt{L_x^2 + L_y^2}$ plane, and the $L_z - \sqrt{J_r}$ plane.

These quantities have been identified by previous workers in their searches for different kinematic signatures. Thus, searching in the $U - V$ plane identifies kinematic over-densities, irrespective of their orbits or assumptions about the Galaxy potential. V is proportional to L_z , a vertical component of the angular momentum, and is an integral of motion in axisymmetric potentials, while $\sqrt{U^2 + 2V^2}$ is a measure of orbital eccentricity. L_z and $\sqrt{L_x^2 + L_y^2}$ are integrals of motion, used in searches for stars on similar orbits. The most general search for kinematic structures is in action space (conserved quantities in stellar orbits), and their final search uses the radial and azimuthal actions J_r and L_z that quantify orbital eccentricity and orbital angular momentum.

And Gaia is central to these sorts of structural studies because all of the quantities needed for characterising stellar orbits require knowledge of their distances, proper motions, and radial velocities.

In $U - V$ velocity space (figure below), and in angular momentum space, the Arcturus stream, along with other known streams (Sirius, Pleiades, Hyades, Hercules, AF06, and KFR08) are clearly identified, all separated by about 20–30 km s⁻¹ in azimuthal velocity, V .

While the Hercules stream appears to be a mixture of thin and thick disk stars, the Arcturus stream (as well as the AF06 and KFR08 streams) is a high-velocity and low-angular momentum structure with chemical composition similar to the thick disk, and extending further from the Galactic plane than the Hercules stream. Kushniruk & Bensby (2019) concluded that the Arcturus stream, together with the AF06 and KFR08 streams, have properties different to those expected for bar-driven structures, and are instead likely to be part of a ‘phase-space wave’ that could have been caused by an ancient merger event.

More and improved Gaia data will follow in the future, but the present results appear to confirm the earlier conclusions of Minchev et al. (2009), or possibly Navarro et al. (2004) and Helmi et al. (2006), but in any case convincingly exclude its origin as an evaporating cluster.

I will finish this part with a reflection from Navarro et al. (2004): ‘It is oddly gratifying to think of stars visible to the naked eye, such as Arcturus, as silent night-sky witnesses of the merging history of the Milky Way.’

Kushniruk & Bensby (2019)

LET ME NOW turn to HR 1614, another overdensity in velocity space, discovered and classified as a nearby moving group by Eggen (1978). He identified about 40 stars (including HR 1614) with a mean rotational velocity $V \simeq -60$ km s⁻¹, higher than solar metallicity, an age of ~ 5 Gyr, and which he attributed to an old dissolving cluster. It was re-examined using Hipparcos data by Feltzing & Holmberg (2000), and also explained as a disrupting metal-rich open cluster, but of age ~ 2 Gyr.

Kushniruk et al. (2020) used Gaia DR2 astrometry, with APOGEE and GALAH spectroscopy, to refine the group membership and kinematics, with the aim of further clarifying its origin.

They found that the group does not form an ‘arch’ of constant energy in $U - V$ space, and is tilted in V . Its stars have a wide range of metallicities, ages, and abundances, similar to the thin and thick disks. They conclude that it is not a dissolving open cluster, or an accreted population, but rather has a complex origin perhaps best explained by several different mechanisms such as resonances with the Galactic bar and spiral structure, phase mixing of dissolving spiral structure, and phase mixing due to an external perturbation.

Kushniruk et al. (2020)

IN THESE LAST two essays I have considered just three of the kinematic moving groups or streams in the solar neighbourhood. Recently, Lucchini et al. (2023) described a new open-source 2D wavelet transformation code, MGwave, based on similar wavelet techniques used in previous searches, but also allowing for the investigation of underdensities, presumably also relevant in probing the Milky Way’s non-axisymmetric features.

Applied to the latest Gaia data release, DR3, they detected 47 groups of stars with coherent velocities, recovering the majority of the previously known moving groups, as well as identifying three additional significant candidates: one within Arcturus, and two in regions without much substructure at low V_R , and extending the searches to Galactocentric radii 6.5–10 kpc.

PROBING THE kinematic structure of stars near the Sun, as revealed by Gaia, is clearly proving to be a powerful tool for untangling the structure of our Milky Way. With improving data, numerous complex kinematic structures are being better characterised, and new ones continue to be discovered.